

FROM PROTESTS TO PETITIONS: THE GLOBAL RESPONSE TO THE GAZA CRISIS SINCE OCTOBER 2023

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Abstract

This paper discusses the global civilian response to the Israeli massacre in Gaza since October 2023. The massacre began when Hamas carried out an attack on October 07 that was retaliated with indiscriminate attacks by the Israeli regime. Israel carried out massacres not only through military strikes but also by blockading Gaza by stopping the entry of food, water, electricity, and internet aid in Gaza. This has increased the number of deaths in Gaza and people suffering acutely. The international community responded to this Israeli attack through condemnation, criticism, and calls to stop this massacre. This study will focus on the efforts of the global civil community in responding to the Israeli massacre in Gaza by trying to map the spread of actions and strategies carried out by these communities. This study uses a qualitative method approach by collecting data through online media to assess the actions and movement patterns of the global community's efforts to respond to the Gaza issue and the Israeli massacre.

Keywords: *Global Civic Action, Israel, Protests, Gaza Massacre*

Introduction

October 07, 2023, Hamas carried out a cross-border attack on Israel in a clandestine and organized manner through land, sea, and air strikes against Israel from the Gaza Strip. In response to the attacks, Israel declared a state of war alert and began mobilizing its army reservists to prepare for retaliatory attacks. Israel also carried out airstrikes on the Gaza Strip. They

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bombarded Gaza with fighter jets until many ruins of houses and buildings hit the Palestinian population ([Britannica 2024](#)).

Israel's attacks have impacted to many lives and destroyed infrastructure due to its attacks since October 07, 2023. According to BBC International on February 13, 2024, more than 28,000 Palestinians have been killed, including Palestinian children and women ([BBC 2024](#)). Based on Al-Jazeera reporting by taking data from the Palestinian Ministry of Health and the Palestine Red Crescent Society, until the 179th day of the conflict has claimed tens of thousands of casualties due to Israeli attacks, both civilians, journalists, humanitarian activists, doctors, and other health workers ([AJLabs 2023](#)). Infrastructure has also been destroyed. As of March 28, 2024, Israeli attacks have damaged more than 360,000 housing units, 396 educational facilities, 10 of the 35 hospitals are partially functioning, 83% of groundwater wells are unusable, 267 places of worship are destroyed, and 11 stores of staple food production (bread) were damaged ([AJLabs 2023](#)).

The massacres committed by Israel against Palestine invite the sympathy of the global community to support Palestine in various activities and to condemn Israel. Not only the state but also various humanitarian activists are active in protesting and pressure to voice their concern for the Israeli massacre in Palestine. This study will review various protest measures from community groups in various countries to respond to the Israeli-Zionist massacre in Gaza, Palestine, since October 07, 2023.

The social movement approach is the approach used in this study. Social movement is defined as an effort by certain communities or non-state actors to fight for social change. There are three characteristic of a social movement group. First: it is involved in conflict relations with parties considered to cause the problem; second: the communities or activists are bound by an informal but compact network. Even though for example they

are not in the same organization, but the existence of a common vision and enemies makes them unite to fight for their interests; the third is the existence of a collective consciousness that binds the members involved in the change effort (Della Porta and Diani, 2006). To fight for its interests, social movements carry out various actions, both peaceful in scale and using violent means, for example, making petitions, demonstrations, strikes, lobbying and various other activities either directly or through online media (Loya and McLeod 2020).

Research Methodology

This study uses a qualitative research approach to investigate the global civilian response to Israel's murder in Gaza since October 7, 2023. Data was gathered by examining online media sources such as news stories, social media posts, and reports from international organizations and NGOs. Key events, protest actions, and civic movements were identified and mapped to better understand these responses' geographic distribution and character. The data was analyzed thematically to find similar trends, techniques, and outcomes of worldwide civil actions.

Result and Discussion

The Global Civic Movement Actions in Respons to Israel's Massacre of Gaza

Israel's massive attack on Gaza triggered an international public response in various ways, including through protests or demonstrations. These protests took place in various continents of countries and cities around the world, they demonstrated with the slogan "Free Palestine" as a form of humanitarian support and concern for the calamity experienced by Palestine. ACLED recorded 4,200 protests around the world since the first

three weeks of Israel's assault on Gaza ([Murillo 2023](#)). According to ACLED since October 7 to 27, 2023 that protests have taken place in the Middle East and North Africa continent as many as 1,400 demonstration activities, Yemen with 490 activities, Turkey with 357 activities, Iran with 276 activities, and Morocco with 267 activities ([Murillo 2023](#)). Furthermore, according to Al Jazeera, protests taking place in Africa and the Middle East took place in 8 countries and 8 cities, namely in Egypt (Cairo), South Africa (Cape Town), Morocco (Rabat), Jordan (Amman), Iraq (Baghdad), Lebanon (Beirut), Bahrain (Manama) and Iran (Tehran) ([Ali 2023](#)). Several hundred people gathered outside the offices of the Zionist Federation, shouting "Boycott Apartheid Israel" and "There's no right side to genocide" ([Staff 2023](#)).

In Morocco and Bahrain, protests demand the cancellation of the normalization of their governments' relations with Israel, which is considered responsible for the oppression of Palestinians. In Cairo, they raised giant flags in downtown Cairo and shouted against the Israeli occupation of Muscat ([Yee 2023](#)). In Lebanon, protesters gathered in front of the French embassy to express their frustration at international support for Israel. They called on French President Emmanuel Macron and the rest of the international community to take stronger action against the protection of human rights ([Salhani 2023](#)).

In Europe, protest demonstrations took place in 12 countries and 18 cities including in Spain (Barcelona), Greece (Athens), Switzerland (Geneva), Germany (Berlin), England (Cambridge, London and Manchester), Denmark (Copenhagen), Turkey (Diyarbakır and İstanbul), Italy (Milan, Paris, Rome and Turin), the Netherlands (The Hague), Ireland (Dublin) and Scotland (Edinburgh and Glasgow) ([Ali 2023](#)). In Rome, nearly a thousand protesters marched holding signs that read "Palestine, Rome is with you" and "No Peace until we get freedom" ([Seçkin 2023](#)). In Germany, protests by civil society took place on Adenauerplatz Square. The

demonstrators criticized Germany's pro-Israel stance. The protesters carried signs that read "Cease-fire now" and "Stop The Genocide" ([Karadag 2023](#)). In London, England, tens of thousands of people took to the streets of the city center to call for a permanent ceasefire ([HUI 2023](#)).

Asian Publics also actively hold the protests against Israel's attack on Gaza such as in Sri Lanka (Colombo), India (Delhi, Hyderabad, Kargil, Kolkata Lucknow, Mumbai, Pune, Thiruvananthapuram), Pakistan (Islamabad, Karachi and Lahore), Bangladesh (Dhaka), South Korea (Seoul), Japan (Tokyo), Syria (Damascus), Palestine (Nablus), Yemen (Sana'a), Indonesia (Jakarta and Surakarta) and Malaysia (Kuala Lumpur) ([Ali 2023](#)). Of all the Asian countries, that one of the largest protests in Asia was in Indonesia on November 05, 2023, at the National Monument Square (Monas), Jakarta by hundreds of thousands of people who gathered to demanding a ceasefire. In Malaysia, protested by gathering at one of the football stadiums in Terengganu by waving flags "Free Palestine" as a form of support ([McGrath 2023](#)).

In the USA, civil society also demonstrated against Israeli tyranny. There are 5 countries, and 19 cities are the scene of mass demonstrations. These countries and cities are the United States (Boston, Dallas, Dearborn, LA, New York, Pittsburgh, Tucson, Washington), Brazil (Brasília, Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo), Canada (Calgary, Edmonton, Mississauga, Montreal, Vancouver), Venezuela (Cape Town, Caracas) and Chile (Santiago) ([Ali 2023](#)). Protests in Latin American regions such as Brazil, Venezuela, and Bolivia demanded a ceasefire and freedom for Palestinians by raising Palestinian flags ([Dogan 2024](#)). In Washington, thousands of demonstrators gathered from the White House, precisely at Freedom Plaza. The narratives they voiced questioned the viability of President Joe Biden as a presidential candidate at the time. The demonstrators held up posters that read "No votes for Genocide Joe," "Biden has blood on his hands," and "Let Gaza live" ([Jackman dkk. 2024](#)).

Australia has also been the scene of civilian protests Israel's assault on Gaza. The [\(Levy 2023\)](#) action took place in two countries and seven cities, namely Australia (Brisbane, Adelaide, Canberra, Melbourne, Sydney, Adelaide) and New Zealand (Auckland). Demonstrators in Australia gathered in major Australian cities, such as Sydney and Melbourne. They marched for weeks, calling for a permanent ceasefire movement by raising flags, banners, and placards raised high by chanting the slogans "free Palestine" and "stop genocide now" [\(Levy 2023\)](#). The protest by Australians has drawn condemnation and threats from Australian authorities. The response issued by the authorities to the protests was to impose arbitrary restrictions or arrests on demonstrators deemed not peaceful [\(CIVICUS 2024\)](#).

Internally, there are also demonstrations carried out by Israelis both inside and outside the state of Israel, such as thousands of Israelis who protested in Tel Aviv and other Israeli cities to call for a ceasefire, an end to the crime of genocide, and demand that Benjamin Netanyahu (Prime Minister of Israel) step down from government positions [\(Aljazeera 2024c\)](#). Abroad, as in the United States, Israelis led by the Jewish community in America also protested by occupying the Statue of Liberty, Congress, the Great California Bridge, the Bloomberg Building, and other locations in denial of crimes committed by the Israeli government against Palestinians [\(Center 2024\)](#).

Not only protests, the global community also carried out a petition to call for an Israeli-Gaza ceasefire in the UK since October 16, 2023 this petition has obtained as many as 466,416 signatures from the London and Global communities [\(M B 2023\)](#). In Indonesia, a public petition has also been carried out in support of South Africa against Israel at the International Court of Justice (ICJ) since January 05, 2024, this petition has received 62,677 signatures [\(Amd 2024\)](#).

One of the massive issues as part of the protests against Israeli massacres has been the rise of calls to boycott products that have ties to Israel. The boycott call resonated globally in the Islamic world, Europe, America, Africa, and other countries. In Indonesia, the boycott action was strengthened by the issuance of MUI fatwa No. 83 regarding the law supporting the Palestinian cause. This fatwa regulates that helping fight for Palestinian independence against Israeli occupation is mandatory, and this fatwa also stipulates recommendations that urge Muslims to avoid making transactions and using products that are affiliated with or support the occupation. These products include McDonald's, Starbucks, Burger King, Coca-Cola, Pepsi, and others ([N 2023](#)).

In the Middle East, there are many boycotts campaigns against several products in the Middle East region including in Jordan, Kuwait, Morocco and Egypt where those people join to boycott some Western Products including McDonald's, Kentucky Fried Chicken (KFC) and Starbucks ([Al-Khalidi dan Farah Saafan 2023](#)).

Social media is one of the most important means for the world public to voice their concerns about Gazans. Global netizens disseminated photos and videos of Israeli terrorism. Through social media, activists and figures have also condemned Israel.

The Indonesian and Malaysian public specifically introduced the Julid Fi Sabilillah movement called on Twitter to fight Zionism and Israel by counter-narratives, Indonesian and Malaysian netizens carried out this movement as one of the efforts to fight Zionism and Israel on social media, the object of Julid Fi Sabilillah was the Israeli army, police officers, and Israeli citizens on social media ([Saputra 2024](#)). Julid Fi Sabilillah's actions were carried out by terrorizing the Israeli military's social media accounts, accompanied by sharp comments. This action proved effective, weakening the targeted account and causing the account owner to be threatened and

disturbed, as a result of which the action made many Israeli soldiers express anxiety and complaints because of sharp words that were able to successfully bring them down.

The Impacts of Global Civil Society Actions

The demonstration that occurred in various parts of the world attracts many local and international media related to crimes committed by Israel and the humanitarian crisis in Palestine such as Cable News Network and New York Times (United States), Aljazeera (Qatar), Tempo and Kompas (Indonesia), The Guardians (UK), as well as the Australian Broadcasting Corporation (Australia).

The impact of this demonstration provides awareness and attracts the sympathy of the global community to jointly support and voice humanity and justice by rejecting the crime of genocide committed by Israel against Palestinians. This can be seen from the large number of participants in many countries who are actively involved in providing support for Gazans and condemnation of Israel and pressuring major countries such as the US and its allies to act more effectively to support the ceasefire in Gaza ([Lesmana 2023](#)).

These demonstrations also creates pressure on governments in a country to be more active in resolving the humanitarian crisis in Palestine and pressure the world community and governments to impose sanctions and take tougher action to stop the crime of genocide against Israel as some countries such as Colombia, Chile, Bahrain, Jordan, and Bolivia have done by boycotting and withdrawing ambassadors or severing diplomatic relations with Israel in response to Israel's crimes and exerting pressure to stop its crimes ([Hanum 2023](#)).

The impact of protests also occurred in the United States. The Biden administration, which initially used its veto power to support Israel in three U.N.-proposed ceasefire resolutions, abstained from attempting a fourth UN resolution in March 2024. The US administration has also begun to look to provide humanitarian assistance to Gazans, including urging Israel not to launch a full-scale attack on Rafah citing concern for civilians ([Aljazeera 2024a](#)), ([Haryono 2024](#)).

In South Africa, thousands of Pro - Palestinian demonstrators taking place in major cities in South Africa such as Johannesburg and Cape Town resulted in South Africa's decision on December 29, 2023 to apply to the international court of justice (ICJ) to issue an urgent order stating that Israel had violated its obligations to comply with agreements based on the 1948 Genocide Convention ([Aljazeera 2024b](#)).

In the Indonesian context, the impact of the demonstrations encouraged the Indonesian government through the Indonesian Minister of Foreign Affairs, Retno Marsudi to actively provide support for Palestine in the international arena in rejecting crimes committed by Israel and calling on the global community to stop the violence that occurred ([Yoga 2023](#)). The minister realized this support by conveying Indonesia's support for Palestine at the UN forum and inviting all countries to jointly reject the crime of genocide committed by Israel ([Chaterine 2023](#)).

On the one hand, through various social media platforms such as X, Instagram, and Facebook, many influencers are collaborating with humanitarian agencies to invite the global community to provide humanitarian assistance to the crisis in Gaza as Atta Halilintar did with the humanitarian organization “Hati Baik” by opening donations for Palestine

care on October 25, 2023 through the KitaBisa platform, The amount of donations collected reached hundreds of millions of rupiah. Likewise, through Teuku Wisnu's personal Instagram upload, fundraising for Palestine reached 2 billion rupiah ([Noviandi 2023](#)).

In addition to humanitarian aid, social media is a place to call for boycotts of products affiliated with Israel. The massive call is evident from the results of the journal's research analysis which concluded that the consistency of the topic of product boycotts is very high on social media, especially platform X. The sentiment of many Indonesian netizens strongly agrees with the boycott of pro-Israel products is positive. Many Indonesian netizens fully support the boycott of pro-Israel products ([Munandar, Yaasin, dan Firdaus 2023](#)).

Through the *Julid Fii Sabilillah* movement on social media, which was carried out massively, it had an impact on the mentality and morale of the Israeli police and soldiers as well as Israeli institutions that voiced anti-Palestine. Often hashtags #JulidFiSabilillah become the main topic on platform X, this is a form of global support for Palestine. *Julid Fi Sabilillah's* strategic action by terrorizing the Israeli military's social media accounts, which was accompanied by various sharp comments. These actions have proven effective, weakening targeted accounts and causing account owners to be compromised and compromised. As a result, this action made many Israeli soldiers express anxiety and grievances because of the sharp words that were able to successfully bring them down mentally ([BNNbreaking 2023](#)).

Through the social movement approach, the global actions carried out in various countries—demonstrations, petitions, calls for boycotts, and actions on social media—align with three main variables of social movements. First, these global movements identify Israel as the primary perpetrator of the violations occurring in Gaza. Second, these movements

consist of thousands of individuals and communities joining together globally with a single goal, even though they are not part of the same organizational network. Third, the sole unifying factor for these actions is the concern for the condition of Gaza's residents, who are being killed and massacred by Zionist Israel, whether through military means or otherwise.

Conclusion

The global response to the violations in Gaza shows a powerful social movement defined by three major factors. Firstly, these measures designate Israel as the primary perpetrator of the horrors in Gaza. Second, despite not being part of a single organizational network, thousands of individuals and groups worldwide are working together to achieve a common goal. Third, the common thread connecting these actions is real concern for the condition of Gaza's population, who are subjected to brutality and massacres at the hands of Zionist Israel, whether by military force or other means. This immense mobilization demonstrates the strength of global solidarity and the ability of social movements to address and challenge international injustices. Furthermore, the continuous global attention and activism reflect social media and digital platforms' expanding role in amplifying underrepresented perspectives and igniting global collective action.

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